

Equivalent elastic properties of morphing sandwich panels with cellular cores and flexible facesheets

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1. Background

Semi-Aeroelastic Hinge

Extended wingspan in flight, folded wingtip when approaching airport gate.

Flare angle helps to alleviate gust load. [1]

A morphing fairing needed to cover the hinge joint.

The objective is to design a fairing with low torsional stiffness and low cross-section warping as the wingtip folds.

2. Overall Design Problem

Morphing sandwich panel with cellular core and elastomeric facesheets for fairing. [2]

Homogenisation of panel elastic properties to equivalent shell stiffness matrix.

Finite element model with equivalent thin-walled shell fairing and rigid ribs.

Goal: Parametric study of the design space by varying core geometry, panel thickness and local orientation, and pre-tension across the hinge.

3. Homogenization

Cores with zero, negative and positive Poisson's ratios are analysed.

Analytical Approach

Equivalent elastic properties (i.e., E_{11} , E_{22} , ν_{12} , G_{12}) of the core evaluated by considering deformation of unit cell walls. [3]

Shell stiffness matrix evaluated for a panel with isotropic facesheets and equivalent core.

Finite Element Approach

Shell deformation modes of a unit cell with multiscale periodic boundary conditions are used to evaluate equivalent shell stiffness matrix. [4]

Equivalent 2D constitutive response							
A_{11}	A_{12}	A_{16}	B_{11}	B_{12}	B_{16}		
A_{22}	A_{26}		B_{22}	B_{26}	B_{26}		
sym		A_{66}	sym			B_{66}	
	sym		D_{11}	D_{12}	D_{16}		
			sym	D_{22}	D_{26}	D_{16}	
						D_{66}	

4. Preliminary Results

Significant error in analytical values relative to the FEA values.

Future work should explore the nonlinearities in the elastic response.

